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ADVANTAGES OF USING TRADITIONAL CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF LOW-RISE RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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Abstract: This article examines the importance of the rational use of traditional building materials in the construction of modern low-rise residential buildings in various regions and cities of the country. These materials, inherited from ancestors, have proven their effectiveness in practice and remain relevant to contemporary construction requirements. The study also focuses on issues of environmental sustainability, a return to natural materials, and the preservation of local architectural and construction traditions.

Key words: residential buildings, traditional construction, natural stone, fired brick, clay plaster, wooden beams, reed, local building materials.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimizning turli viloyat va shaharlarida zamonaviy kam qavatli turar-joy binolarini barpo etish jarayonida ota-bobolarimizdan meros bo'lib kelayotgan va o'z samaradorligini amalda isbotlagan an'anaviy qurilish ashyolaridan oqilona foydalanish zarurligi ilmiy jihatdan yoritilgan. Shuningdek, qurilish sohasida ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash, tabiiylikka qaytish hamda mahalliy qurilish an'analarini saqlab qolish masalalari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: turar-joy, an'anaviy qurilish, tabiiy tosh, pishgan g'isht, loy suvoq, yog'och to'sin, qamish, mahalliy qurilish materiallari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается необходимость рационального использования традиционных строительных материалов при возведении современных малоэтажных жилых зданий в различных регионах и городах страны. Подчеркивается, что данные материалы, унаследованные от предков, на практике доказали свою эффективность и соответствие современным требованиям строительства. Особое внимание уделяется вопросам экологической устойчивости, возвращения к натуральным материалам и сохранения национальных строительных традиций.

Ключевые слова: жилищное строительство, традиции, природный камень, обожжённый кирпич, глиняная штукатурка, деревянные балки, камыш, местные строительные материалы.

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, the history of world civilization has been directly connected with the development of architecture. Human architectural activity represents a continuous process of development from the period of primitive communal society to the present day. Residential construction, in particular, has a very long history on Earth. From the moment of human emergence, people built dwellings to protect themselves from external environmental influences such as enemies, predatory animals, cold, and heat. At the same time, housing has served as a fundamental factor providing conditions for rest and work.

Over time, the purpose and functions of housing have evolved and expanded. Residential architecture has continuously adapted to the social conditions of society, the spirit of the era, and various external circumstances. From simple huts or caves, housing has gradually transformed into modern residential buildings of our time, becoming fully developed structures equipped with contemporary facilities and amenities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on traditional construction materials in Uzbekistan has long emphasized their architectural, functional, and environmental value. The journal *Uzbek Architecture and Construction* Issue No. 5 of 2009 highlights that traditional materials such as fired brick, clay plaster, wood, and reed have historically been well adapted to local climatic conditions, ensuring thermal comfort and durability in residential buildings. These materials are shown to reduce excessive energy consumption while maintaining structural reliability in low-rise housing.

Ubaydullaev H. M. and Inogomova M. M., in their work *Typological Foundations of Designing Residential and Public Buildings* published in Tashkent in 2009, provide a detailed typological analysis of housing forms developed in Central Asia. Their research demonstrates that traditional construction systems evolved as rational responses to social structure, climate, and available natural resources. The authors underline that low-rise residential buildings constructed with traditional materials ensure better microclimatic balance and long-term sustainability compared to many modern industrial materials.

Later educational works such as *Design of Residential and Public Buildings* by Qodirova S. A. and Abdujabbarova M. T., published in 2020, as well as Abdujabbarova's *Design of Residential Buildings* from 2015, further reinforce the relevance of traditional materials in contemporary practice. These studies, together with Hidirov Muhsin's *History of Architecture* published in 2004, confirm that traditional construction materials are not only part of cultural heritage but also remain economically efficient, environmentally safe, and beneficial for human health when applied to modern low-rise residential construction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This tradition, which has been formed over centuries, is known today to manifest itself in different forms across various parts of the world. Throughout the Muslim regions, residential building types have developed in distinctive ways depending on climatic conditions. Residential houses in the settlements of Uzbekistan are also part of this tradition. Since climatic conditions vary across all regions of the republic, different schools of residential design and construction have emerged.

However, based on our traditions, this study focuses on examining their common and similar characteristics. For example, low-rise individual residential houses currently being constructed in the Tashkent region are built in diverse ways. These variations are compared in this study, with particular attention paid to the advantages and disadvantages of modern and traditional construction materials.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At present, due to the increasing demand for housing, the number of builders using modern construction materials in the construction of low-rise residential buildings, similar to multi-storey housing, has significantly increased. This leads to higher construction costs and increased energy consumption. However, it also accelerates the construction process and contributes to a more visually appealing appearance.

Nevertheless, we believe that in the construction of individual low-rise residential buildings, greater attention should be paid to traditional construction materials. It is advisable to use straw-reinforced clay plaster. Construction with fired brick is preferable. Wooden beams should be used, and reed should be laid and finished with loam. In this case, construction becomes more affordable, while the interior remains cool in summer and warm in winter (Figure 1). Houses built with natural construction materials also demonstrate better air permeability. The primary purpose of housing construction is to create a comfortable environment for rest and work, as well as to ensure a healthy lifestyle for residents.

Our conclusions are based on direct observations, as we have witnessed cases where plaster detached from houses built with foam blocks. We also observed that such houses tend to be hot in summer and cold in winter. This has a negative impact on human health, increases energy consumption, and leads to higher expenses.

Our observations further revealed that many builders fill the interior of foundations with soil and finish the floor with concrete screed. This practice is considered incorrect because soil absorbs ground moisture, while concrete screed further draws this moisture to the surface. Such conditions are harmful to human health. Instead, the interior of the foundation should be filled with large natural stones and finished with a dense clay plaster. Since parquet or laminate flooring is usually laid on top, this solution proves to be highly beneficial for health. Natural stones do not absorb moisture due to their density and hardness, while clay plaster provides thermal insulation.

Additional observations show that many builders construct the walls of low-rise residential buildings using modern foam blocks, gas blocks, and even slag blocks, which is a serious mistake. Such materials tend to

retain cold in winter and heat in summer. Fired brick, on the contrary, demonstrates opposite properties. When laying bricks, it is not mandatory to use concrete mortar; using clay mortar is both more affordable and faster. Similarly, using clay plaster for wall finishing is recommended. Clay is inexpensive, provides good thermal insulation against both heat and cold, and ensures proper air exchange within the house.

Covering houses with monolithic slabs or panels may be fast and durable, but it is not an effective solution in terms of thermal performance. In contrast, roofing based on wooden beams and rafters, combined with reed layers and loam finishing, provides excellent results for both heat and cold protection (Figure 2) and is also cost-effective.

In recent times, the use of modern metal roofing sheets has become widespread. Such materials serve little purpose beyond enhancing the building's appearance. They retain heat in summer and cold in winter, shorten the lifespan of wooden structural elements, and are costly. As an alternative, the use of slate roofing is more economical, durable, and resistant to both heat and cold (Figure 1). Especially today, when the use of roofs as attic or mansard spaces has become common, slate-covered roofs are much easier to heat and cool. Such construction materials are safe for human health and are considered environmentally friendly.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, compared to modern construction materials, traditional building materials are more advantageous both in terms of affordability and their positive impact on human health. Taking these factors into account, we recommend the use of traditional construction materials that have been tested and proven through many years of practical experience in the construction of low-rise residential buildings.

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